

Identity Politics and the Practice of Social Work in South-South Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the emergence of social work practice in South-South Nigeria. The introduction of social work practice in this region is at the instance of identity politicians who have relentlessly ensured that the militarization of the region does not affect the area in a way too devastating to the people. Social work is a profession for those with a spark of idealism, a belief in social injustice and the natural love to assist people in need. To actualize our aim, we raised a hypothesis which we tested with the T-test statistical tool and our finding reveals that the militarization of the South-South region led to the emergence of social work practice to cushion the effect of the activities of the military on the people. Again, it became glaring that social work practice can only grow if and when people put aside their inhibitions and confide in the social worker. And so we recommend that the development of this region will ensure peace and that to put aside our taboos divulging information to the social worker would be a panacea to the development of that profession in this country.

Keywords Identity, Politics, Practice, Social Work, South-South, Nigeria.

1. Introduction

Social work is the calling through which social administrations are delivered by expertly appointed people. It is the expert action of aiding people, gatherings, and networks to upgrade or reestablish their ability for social working. Social labourer's help individuals manage their associations with others to tackle their own, family and local area issues, and develop, create by figuring out how to adapt to or shape the social and ecological powers influencing their day by day life.

Social work is accordingly, a calling for those with a sparkle of optimism, a confidence in friendly equity, and a characteristic love to work with individuals. Social works offer the opportunity to work with and for individuals, everything being equal: rich or poor, old or youthful, in medical clinics, old, people with incapacities, people with requirements of wellbeing and psychological well-being care. Social work practice in South-South Nigeria deals with a few issues and difficulties like frailty, an endless loop of destitution, disparities, and so on in reaction to these issues and difficulties confronting social work in South-South Nigeria, social work specialists are relied upon to procure sufficient abilities and information important to manage these difficulties. To work viably, social work professionals need to consider how individuals live, their difficulties, and their issues. Friendly work specialists in South-South Nigerian ought to have the proficient skill, commitment to work, consistency to morals of calling and stringently noticing the training standards with high trustworthiness. For the effect of social work to be felt, social experts should adjust to the accompanying: capability, certainty and boldness.

Here, we endeavour to underscore the exercises of the social specialist, given the way that the issue of personality governmental issues prompts everywhere of the locale. Personality legislative issues is a solid

name for all types of sectional interest pointed toward accomplishing acknowledgement and freedom of people and assign bunches whose individuals are viewed as "pariahs". As a scholarly talk, personality governmental issues accept the presence of imbalance, bad form and persecution in the general public. Its down to earth importance is inserted in its handiness in the comprehension of issues on friendly segregations dependent on identity, religion, prejudice, exchange, unionism and sexual orientation (Uzorka, 2015). Its sectional direction underlines love for one's gathering. Its goal is that of acknowledgement, recovery and redefinition of marks of disgrace and detriments related to the underestimated bunch. Our emphasis is on the investigation of South-South Nigeria where the issue of minimization, destitution and monetary foul play is on the expansion on everyday schedule.

Note that the commonness of the above events in the locale has exacerbated the exercises of social work and have additionally made life unlivable for all individuals. Such association as (INC) Ijaw National Congress, Ijaw Youth Congress (IYC), Niger-Delta Youth Movement (NDYM) to specify yet a couple, endeavours to offer the required help through attempting to guarantee that what is for individuals are given them, however, individuals were somewhat treated in a particularly defamatory term as psychological oppressors. Furthermore, as fear mongers, they should be managed unequivocally.

This assessment of the government prompted the militarization of the South-South, with the end goal that today there are more issues and disarray which presently requires the earnest consideration of social labourers around there. Considering the previous, it will be more right than wrong to theorize that the more the Government keep on mobilizing the South-South the more prominent the frequency of character legislative issues around there.

The Concept of Identity Politics

Character governmental issues is a political methodology and investigation dependent on individuals focusing on the worries generally applicable to their specific racial, strict, ethnic, sexual, social and so on, and framing select political coalitions with others of this gathering, rather than participating in more conventional, wide-based gathering legislative issues. The individuals who focus on their specific kind of character legislative issues may advance their gathering's advantage without respect for the interest of bigger, more different political gatherings that are situated in shared hypothesis. Character legislative issues have been utilized to allude to a wide scope of political exercises and hypothetical examination established in encounters of shameful acts shared by various gatherings of people. In this sense, personality governmental issues normally plan to recover more prominent self-assurance and political opportunity for minimized gatherings unmistakable nature and testing outer forced portrayals, rather than getting sorted out conviction frameworks or gathering affiliations.

The term personality governmental issues have been being used in different faculties since the 1960s, yet has been applied with, on occasion, drastically various implications by various individuals. It has acquired prominence with the development of social developments like the women's activist development, the social liberties development in the United States of America, the LGBTQ developments just as a patriot and post-pilgrim developments.

One significant point of personality legislative issues has been for that inclination persecuted by and effectively enduring under foundational social imbalances to verbalize their sufferings and felt abused as far as their insight by cycles of awareness-raising and aggregate activity. Personality legislative issues in the South-South district of Nigeria brought forth different gatherings like the Ijaw National Congress (INC), Ijaw Youth Congress (IYC), and Niger-Delta Youth Movement (NDYM) and so on The fundamental reason and point of these gatherings is to guard the privileges of their individuals and their locale. Individuals of these different gatherings felt persecuted and underestimated, thus, shaped these gatherings to battle for the liberation of their kin and area. Ijaw National Congress (INC) is an agent body framed in 1991; individuals are drawn from among the different constituent networks speaking Ijaw vernaculars. It was shaped to shield and support the interest of the Ijaw ethnic gathering in the Niger Delta. The battle to bring any advantages due to its kin and to be engaged with dynamic in the country.

Ijaw Youth Congress (IYC) is a common right association in Nigeria, established in 1998, which upholds the interests of the Ijaw ethnic gathering of the Niger-Delta in the South-South piece of Nigeria.

Niger-Delta Youth Movement (NDYM) is a non-volunteer army promotion bunch committed to propelling the reason for basic liberties, responsibility and improvement in the Niger-Delta district of Nigeria. The gathering is based on a triple reason to assuage neediness, save the climate and advance work openings for individuals of the Niger Delta, particularly youngsters, Niger Delta tidy up and so forth the gathering participation cuts across the six states in the South-South international zone of Nigeria.

Brief History and Philosophy of Identity Politics

Character legislative issues imply the wide scope of political exercises and conjecturing established in the common encounters of the shamefulness of individuals from certain gatherings of people. The second 50% of the 20th century saw the rise of huge scope political development, in the United States, bunches like Black Civil Rights, Gay and Lesbian freedom, the American Indian Movements; every one of these gatherings put together their cases concerning treacheries done to them. These social developments are undergirded by and encourage a philosophical assortment of writing that takes up inquiries concerning the nature, beginning and fates of the characters being dependant. Character governmental issues as a method of the association are personally associated with the possibility that the gatherings of people are mistreated, that will be, that one's way of life as a lady or as a Native American for instance, makes one exceptionally helpless against social colonialism (counting generalizing, eradication, or allotment of one's gathering character), vicious, misuse, underestimation (Young, 1990). Character governmental issues begin from an examination of abuse to suggest fluidly, the recovering, depiction, change of recently slandered records of gathering enrollment. Maybe than tolerating the negative contents offered by a predominant culture about one's inadequacy, one changes one's own ability to be self-aware local area, regularly through awareness-raising, for instance, in their germinal assertion of Black Feminist character governmental issues, the Combahee River Collective contended that as kids we understood that we were not the same as young men and that we were dealt with contrastingly for instance, when we were advised at the same moment to hush up both for being "refined" cognizance raising really line sharing and developing cognizance, to assemble legislative issues that will transform us and unavoidably end our persecution (Combahee River Collective, 1982).

Concept of Social Work

Social work is a calling that has been created to control the exceptionally enormous and complex human assistance framework set up by society. It is a logical order yet requires an inventive and cunning way to deal with work with people, families, gatherings, and networks that are battling with issues.

A much utilized recorded meaning of social workers showed up in 1959 educational program study supported by CSWE "Social work looks to upgrade the social working of people, separately and in gatherings, by exercises centred upon their social connections which establish the association among man and his current circumstance. These exercises can be assembled into three capacities: Restoration of weakened limit, arrangement of individual and social assets, and counteraction of social brokenness".

The hidden suspicions of social work are:

1. Social work like any remaining callings has issues addressing capacities
2. Social work practice is a demonstration with a logical and worth establishment.
3. Social work practice takes its qualities from those held by the society of which it is a section. Notwithstanding, its qualities are not really or inside and out those generally or prevalently held or rehearsed in the public eye.
4. The logical base of social work comprises of three sorts of information (I) tried information (ii) speculative information that requires change into tried information and (iii) assumptive information or practice astuteness that requires change into theoretical and thereupon into tried information.
5. Social work as a calling appeared and keeps on creating because it addresses human issues and desires perceived by society.

6. The information required for social work practice is dictated by its objectives and capacities, and the issues it tries to address.
7. The disguise of expert information and qualities is an indispensable trait of the expert social specialist since he is himself the instrument of expert assistance.
8. Professional ability is communicated in the exercises of social work.

Social Work in South-South Nigeria

Social work is an arising significant calling in the advanced world. Social work today is used in an assortment of settings and offices. A portion of the significant ones are mental, clinical, marriage, family, school, recovery, amendments, public government assistance, working environment, and so forth Social work is turning out to be more significant because a large number of people are profiting from its administrations and are telling other people who additionally have issues of its numerous qualities and administrations. Individuals are not exclusively being assisted with individual and family issues yet additionally with the neighbourhood, public and surprisingly global troubles. One territory in which social work administrations are growing is in global social work. For a long time, the social work calling has been a significant part of both the American Red Cross and the International Committee of the Red Cross. Worldwide social work administrations have been a significant piece of the United Nations' push to restore war-torn regions to bring help and solace. Sub-Saharan Africa and their battle against AIDS have gotten gigantic consideration and backing from social work. Social work administrations are likewise turning out to be a more significant piece of global reception administrations.

Nigeria is Africa's most crowded country and the tenth biggest on the planet by the populace. Nigeria is made of more than 250 ethnic gatherings. Six geo-political zones, which the South-South is one, this distinction heightens the character legislative issues in the South-South, this had made social work extending in the South-South area. Social work helps individuals who are encountering troubles in their lives, doing social work in the South-South are perplexing term which understanding represents a few difficulties. Social work practice involves various types of opportunities like independence from destitution, disparity and so on Sen (demonstrate year) is of the view assessment that improvement must be more worried about upgrading the life we lead and the opportunity we appreciate. Improvement is considered to mean the persistent accomplishment of all endeavours made by man to address the difficulties in his current circumstance and over his day by day living to accomplish an ideal condition of prosperity.

The requirement for advancement can't be over-underscored. Handelman (2009) is of the view that the most exceedingly awful part of political and financial underdevelopment win in the provincial networks of the most third world. South-South in Nigeria needs most highlights of present-day cultures. This highlights the need to see the advancement of the South-South with a more noteworthy level of earnestness. In the dispersion of social help or social work like schools, medical services, lodging, power, safe water, ecological occupation concerns, the South-South fall behind. The social state of the South-South in Nigeria has for some time been disregarded and consigned. In the South-South, the truth on the ground is that, the area sob for dire intercession of government, non-legislative associations. The South-South has a place with the weak class as they are generally bamboozled with regards to the arrangement of social administrations. Social assistance or social work arrangement has not been met in the South-South in Nigeria (Emmeriyi and Jolly, 2005) is of the assessment that we would, in general, underestimate a portion of the fundamental administrations. Like well-being, training, foundation, and so forth In any case, presently, obviously, everyone understands that without great well-being, essential schooling, and so forth One can't push ahead. This had made the South-South persistently fomenting for the advancement and improvement of the locale, combined with the acceptance that the area gives the assets which the country get its income or pay to run the country, subsequently, feels that they merit better treatment.

UNDP's report of 1999 uncovered that the arrangement, access and utilization of essential social administrations, were difficulties going up against the South-South. The report especially featured the

entirely miserable condition of schooling and climate in the South-South district of Nigeria. Regardless of the appreciation and acknowledgement of the basic arrangement of social administrations, execution is to a great extent an issue of ceaseless discourse. Unfortunately, social work administrations of improvement have not been given the sufficient and merited consideration it requires. The push to build up the locale to improve the government assistance of the general population have either been squandered or shortened. However, the locale had as of late got some degree of consideration because of personality governmental issues. Character legislative issues in the South-South created genuine unsettling inside and universally completed by a few personality bunches which had caused to notice the locale and individuals.

2. Empirical Review

Personality governmental issues incorporate raising its disciples to acknowledge and guard bunch objectives. Like Max's investigation of a gathering in itself and a gathering for itself (Anderson, 1977). In a work done by Heyes, 2002, he thought that "Essentialism" is ill-conceived speculation of personalities. He consequently advised that the perspective of the tried and true way of thinking, disconnection and extension of a specific character of certain people for whole gathering acknowledgement may flag an off-base impression of consistency of the entirety of upsides of such a gathering, while in all actuality, personality involves a perplexing arrangement of various qualities which are overlooked in inclination for another. The expression "ill-conceived speculation" indicates the way that the need esteem which all members are assembled to acknowledge may not be the inclination of each individual from the gathering. At last, he inferred that allies of personality governmental issues through awareness arousing are normally assembled to acknowledge the gathering meaning of the circumstance. Again Anikpo and Alavi, (n-d) in their examination noticed that topic of personality legislative issues is geological and social. This is to say that the marvel is pervasive in all countries of the world; nonetheless, it is more predominant in multi-social orders with sectional consummation for financial, political and social strength as it is being capable right now in South-South Nigeria.

Character legislative issues are more serious in nations that went through imperialism given fake joining of political units paying little mind to social, financial, and social liking and in their decision, they stay away from that governmental issues of personality should consistently receive the position of governmental issues of acknowledgement since patriot who controls the post-pilgrim have kept on propagating similar severe governments as the colonialist; idealizing instruments for the upkeep of their advantage to the detriment of the less-favoured.

Likewise, Bagura (1994), in his examination declares that in the quest for political acknowledgement and battle against abuse, fights are regularly utilized as a way to impact a change and accomplish requests of the gathering. These fights might be as damage and disturbance of routine metro obligations inside the influenced territory, and others, henceforth, it very well may be exceptionally brutal. Exhibitions by underestimated bunches as is normal in South-South district is unexpectedly coordinated by political mobilizers to press for their privileges.

He further proceeded to say that such dissent nonetheless, might be tranquil or savage and that the demonstration of brutality is typically utilized by the wronged to show reality and urge the public authority to reevaluate their cases. Moreover, it is utilized as a type of activating members; brutality is additionally a technique to apply political impact and social authenticity through the politicization of issues of hardships and underestimation.

Identity Politics and Social Work in South-South Nigeria

Social work is workmanship, science, and calling that assist individuals with settling individual gathering, and local area issues and accomplishes fulfilling individual, gathering, and local area connections through friendly work practice. The significant spotlight is on diminishing issues in human connections and enhancing expectations for everyday comforts through improved human communication (Farley and Smith, 2006). The principal point and reason for social work is the advancement of a spot and its kin, on account of the South-South. Both in principle and by and by, advancement is as inconsistent as its

intricacy related to improvement. The irregularity and intricacy as it concerns or is identified with this are defilement, minimization and mistreatment of the South-South locale which feed the country.

Because of the minimization, defilement, and out and out persecution, social work exercises or advantages have not been truly appreciated by the area. The South-South district of Nigeria involves Abia, Akwa-Ibom, Bayelsa, Cross River, Delta, Edo, Imo, Ondo and Rivers State, with an all-out land space of around 75,000 square kilometres and comprised of one hundred and 85 neighbourhood government territories. The area offers more than 90% to the Nigerian economy (Nwagwugwu, Emmanuel and Egwuonwu, 2012). They are the oil delivering states; investigation of oil upset the indigenous habitat of individuals which influenced their methods for vocation. This has made the locale monetarily, socially, and politically flimsy because of unremitting disturbances and fights by individuals. Normally, such a district should encounter an equivalent and sufficient foundation and human improvement to support the climate as well as fill in as a method for endurance for individuals. Be that as it may, this district is experiencing infrastructural rot and a low human turn of events (Nwagwugwu, Emmanuel and Egwuonwu, 2012).

The response of individuals of the locale to the apparent disregard by the progressive government in the country, the cold-heartedness of the global oil organizations to the predicament of the area brought forth arrangement of various gatherings like IYC, INC, NYDM, MOSOP to refer to a couple, to shield and engender the interest of the district and individuals. Social work had not prevailed because of difficulties, defilement, underestimation and persecution however character legislative issues had brought the issues and the requirements of the locale, and individuals to the information on the world, which had changed the tide of exercises of social work in the district to a perceptible level.

Identity Politics and the Activities of Social Workers in Nigeria

The essential elements of social work - rebuilding, arrangement of assets, and avoidance are interlaced and reliant. Reclamation of impeded social working might be partitioned into corrective and recovery viewpoints. Its corrective viewpoints are to dispose of components that have caused the breakdown of working and its rehabilitative angles, to perceive and reconstruct interactional examples. Representations of reclamation would remember help for getting an amplifier for a halfway hard of hearing youngster or assisting a dismissed forlorn kid with being put in cultivate home. The rehabilitative viewpoint may be helping the one youngster as the person acclimates to the new cultivated home.

Arrangement of assets: social and individual for more powerful working might be partitioned into formative and instructive exercises. The improvement angles are intended to add to the viability of the existing social association. A model would be the administrations of a family, a society that helps two individuals, through individual and conjoint meetings, to see each other better and to open the channels of significant correspondence between them. The instructive range is intended to familiarize general society with explicit conditions and requirements for new or changing social assets. Once more, this could be shown by open talks given by staff individuals from a family administration to society, in which mentoring administrations are portrayed as an asset in lightening marriage and family issues. Avoidance of social brokenness includes early revelation, control, and disposal of conditions and circumstances that conceivably could hamper viable social working. The two fundamental divisions are the anticipation of issues in the space of cooperation among people and gatherings and besides, the avoidance of social ills.

Early directing would be an illustration of an endeavour to forestall individual and social issues according to social working. It is trusted that through this cycle couple will want to expect potential troubles in conjugal cooperation and through satisfactory thought and comprehension, stay away from the issues that may result in any case. Counteraction of social-ills normally falls inside the space of local area association. An illustration of this capacity is the local area administrations gathering way to deal with the decrease of adolescent wrongdoing through the usage of all local area associations and monetary assets, for instance, to assemble another young community and furnish it with an expertly prepared staff to work with young men and young ladies who are close to delinquent or who live in delinquent regions. A

general end in the 1959 educational plan study expresses that the attention on friendly connections, in any case, is recommended as the distinctive attributes of the social work calling.

Harriet Barlett claims that social work is a setup of components none of which is one of a kind however, in the mix, addresses a commitment very particular form that is delivered by some other calling. The 1992 CSWE educational program strategy articulation shows that the calling of social work is focused on the upgrade of human prosperity and the easing of destitution and mistreatment. The social work calling gets its approval from the public and private protection and is the essential calling in the arrangement of social administrations. The 1995 version of the social work word reference characterizes social work as an applied study of assisting individuals with accomplishing a successful degree of psychosocial working and affecting cultural changes to upgrade prosperity, all things considered. A new meaning of social work characterizes it as a craftsmanship, a science and a calling that assists individuals with tackling individual gathering (particularly family), and local area issues and achieving fulfilling individual, gathering, and local area connections through friendly work practice. Social work practice today is frequently hereditary, including each of the three of the conventional techniques. The significant spotlight is on decreasing issues in human connections and on enhancing living through improved human communication.

Social work is craftsmanship; it requires extraordinary abilities to get individuals and to assist them with aiding themselves. It is a starting science given its critical thinking technique and its endeavours to be unbiased in determining realities and in creating standards and operational ideas. It is a calling since it incorporates the properties of a calling.

3. Methodology

The graphic plan was utilized in this investigation to guarantee a definite examination of how the exercises of the military in South-South exacerbated the commonness of legislative issues of personality around there. The number of inhabitants in the examination comprises the whole South-South space of Nigeria and this is 20,643,970 individuals. Be that as it may, utilizing self-developed instrument technique for deciding inspecting size which accentuates value assuming no; we chose 50 respondents from each state. This is so because the entire of South-South is too huge to even think about concentrating in only one examination and dependent on this we have 300 people as our complete respondents/members in the investigation.

The instrument utilized in information assortment is the survey, perception, meet and centred gathering conversation (FGDS). Here certain characters in this investigation territory were met and were occupied with centred gathering conversations. The poll was directed to our respondents and as indigenes of the South-South territory; we had the option to carefully see what occurred and how it occurred in the examination site.

Information Analysis

The invalid speculation brought up in this examination was tried with the measurable strategy for testing information for the particular motivation behind either tolerating or dismissing it. The speculation was in the long run trying with the T-test factual apparatus and it was done at 0.05 degree of importance.

Result

Hypothesis: The more the government of the day continues to militarize the South-South, the greater the incidence of identity politics in the area. In testing this hypothesis, we used an independent t-test statistical tool. The result of the analysis is hereby presented in the table below.

The hypothesis: The more the government continues to militarize the South-South the greater the incidence of identity politics.

T-test statistics on the relationship between the no of solvers and identity politics.

Variables	No	Mean	SD	DF	t-Cal	t-Critical	Remarks
No. of Soldiers	130	47.0	16.0				
Level of Identity Politics	170	53.0	14.0	298	3.2	1.96	N.S

Total	300	100	30	298	3.2	196	
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Sources: Field survey 2020 ($P > 0.05$)

The data on the table above shows that the calculated t-value of 3.2 and 298 is less than the t-critical value of 1.96. It also denotes that the more the no of soldiers in the area, the more the level of identity politics. Based on this, the null hypothesis is therefore retained.

4. Discussion

The information examined showed that there is a huge connection between the no of fighters in the South-South region and the degree of personality governmental issues around there. This finding is upheld by Ake (1994), the perception that the state and its representative of dread motivating through its model demonstrations of viciousness dread and amazement instead of adoration and regard. This essential logical inconsistency innate in the Nigerian state is in reality generally articulated in the oil-bearing networks of the South-South space of the country.

On the record of the prior, people who possess this region, live in steady dread of the obscure and subsequently, brought about the rise of character legislative issues which other than looking for an opportunity for individuals; guaranteed the improvement of social work practice to enhance the sufferings of the occupants of the South-South space of Nigeria. We say this, with the most extreme earnestness and trustworthiness because without the standardization of social work practice in the South-South; the vast majority maybe would have gone crazy given the enduring being dispensed on them on a regular routine. Introduced on the abovementioned, social work practice in South-South space of Nigeria is essentially on mental clinical and restoration and its inexorably turning out to be acknowledged on account of the advantages resultant from it. The point here is that social work practice is just perceived here by those influenced by the exercises of the military. The individuals who are not influenced are yet to see the advantages of social work maybe because it invalidates their qualities. Be that as it may, if our qualities are in change with our practices on how we complete exercises pointed toward bringing harmony and congruity among our kin; at that point, there is a need to incorporate the better approaches forever. Social work practice pointed toward remedying abnormalities in the public arena that were brought about by man in a bid to a glad life. It is a workmanship wherein the information on the study of human relations and the expertise in a relationship is utilized in assembling limits or possibilities in the people or assets locally, proper for better change with part of the whole climate.

5. Conclusion

It is in acknowledgement of the above mentioned, that social work practice was presented in the South-South area to pad the impact of the ruthlessness the occupants endure. We additionally wish to say that the militarization of this locale isn't and can't be the most ideal choice of the public authority. This is because, throughout our examination, we found that with sympathize advancement around there, hostility would be a relic of days gone by and the ordinary way of life of individuals will return.

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